

MODELLING AND OPTIMISATION OF COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF RICE HUSK ASH (RHA) CONCRETE USING SCHEFFE'S THEORY

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Abstract

The study covered the development of model for predicting the compressive strength of rice husk ash (RHA) concrete at 28 days curing age for materials sourced from Afikpo-North Local Government Area of Ebonyi State, Nigeria using Scheffe's (5, 2) simplex lattice design theory to enhance the usage of rice husk ash in order to reduce the cost of cement and concrete production. A total of 30 mix ratios were used to produce 90 concrete cubes of 150mm x 150mm x 150mm size to develop the model and test adequacy using Fisher's test at 95 percent confidence level. The Scheffe's regression model was used to generate the mathematical equation $\hat{Y} = 28.27X_1 + 23.13X_2 + 21.35X_3 + 20.56X_4 + 19.38X_5 + 7.64X_1X_2 - 1.84X_1X_3 - 2.90X_1X_4 - 9.26X_1X_5 + 0.04X_2X_3 - 2.10X_2X_4 - 2.42X_2X_5 - 1.78X_3X_4 - 1.70X_3X_5 - 2.04X_4X_5$ that gave the highest compressive strength of 28.27 N/mm² corresponding to a mix ratio of 0.50:0.95:2.00:4.00:0.05 for w/c ratio, cement, sand, granite and RHA respectively and the minimum compressive strength of 19.38N/mm² corresponding to mix ratio of 0.70:0.75:1.70:3.70:0.25 for w/c ratio, cement, sand, granite and RHA respectively. The study recommended that the rice husk ash used as partial replacement of cement for the model developed should not exceed 17.5% in order to achieve grade C20 concrete

Keywords: Concrete, Compressive Strength, Rice Hush Ash (RHA), Scheffe's Model, Simplex Lattice

Introduction

Housing is one of the most basic human needs. The high cost of cement in Nigeria makes it difficult for most people to build a house thereby increasing the housing deficit in the country due to a teeming population of over 200 million people that need shelter. Concrete is one of the most widely used materials in the world for building construction (Alanerme & Mbadike, 2019; Mohammed et al., 2020). According to Mbadike & Osadebe (2013), concrete is a mixture of several components namely; cement, fine aggregates coarse aggregates and water. The product of these mixture components when hardened sufficiently can be used in various forms to resist load. Among these mixture components, cement is the most expensive material thereby leading to high cost of concrete production in most developing countries of the world (Akeke et.al 2021; Marthong, 2012; Ettu et al., 2016; Muleya et al., 2021). The quests to search for alternative sustainable materials to partially replace cement have been intensified by many researchers over the years to enhance affordance housing for the populace. This study tends to explore the use of rice husk ash (RHA), an agro waste material to partially replace cement in concrete production. Currently, Nigeria is the largest producers of rice in Africa with an annual average volume of 8 million metric tons (Kamai, et al., 2020). Pande and Makarande (2013) posited that rice husk is approximately 20 percent of the paddy yield which after burning in a furnace becomes Rice Husk Ash (RHA). The safe disposal and proper utilization of rice husk posed serious challenge to most countries of the world (Haque, et al., 2021). In other to tackle these challenges, RHA was explored as a sustainable material having been found to be a good pozzolana due to its high silica content that meet the requirements of BS EN 196-3, BS 12 and ASTM C 618 (Fapohunda et. al 2017; Zahid & Kazi, 2019). Compressive strength is one of the most important indicators used for grading concrete structures based on the concrete mix design. Elechi et al. (2022) reported that scholars have previously used empirical method which involved the use of trial mix that leads to material wastages and time to optimise concrete mix design. In order to eliminate these constraints, there is need to develop a way of combining these mixture components optimally so that desired results can be attained. The Scheffe's method using simplex lattice design, a statistical experimental technique has been identified and was used in this research to formulate a predictive model for RHA concrete.

Materials and Methods

Materials

The materials used for this work include cement, fine aggregates, coarse aggregates, water and rice husk ash.

Cement: The Dangote branded Ordinary Portland Cement was used in this work and meets the requirements of NIS 444-1:2018.

Fine Aggregates: The fine aggregates used in this work was clean, sharp sand which is free from deleterious materials obtained from Unwana River Basin, Afikpo

Coarse Aggregates: The coarse aggregates used was crushed granite of maximum size 20mm sourced from ConRock, Amasiri, Afikpo, Ebonyi State.

Water: Portable water was used in this work and meets the requirements of NIS 554:2007.

Rice Husk Ash: Rice husk sourced from Afikpo Rice Mill burnt to Rice Husk Ash through a furnace and sieved using 150 μ m sieve size was used for this work

Methods

Mathematical Modelling Formulation

The Scheffe's second order (q, m) simplex lattice design theory was adopted for this work. Where q is the number of components of the concrete mixture and m is the degree of polynomial function.

According to Onuamah (2014), the sum of all components of a mixture in a Scheffe’s factor space must be equal to one.

$$\sum_{i=1}^q x_i = 1 \quad \text{or} \quad X_1 + X_2 + X_3 + \dots + X_{q-1} + X_q = 1 \quad (1)$$

The concrete mixture ‘q’ is made up of five components namely water, cement, sand, granite and RHA designated as X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4 and X_5 respectively. Where X_i represents the proportion of the i th component in the mixture.

$$\text{Hence,} \quad X_1 + X_2 + X_3 + X_4 + X_5 = 1 \quad (2)$$

The number of coefficients, n , of the polynomial according to Scheffe’s method is given as

$$n = \frac{(q+m-1)!}{(q-1)!m!} \quad (3)$$

m is the degree of the polynomial. Thus for $q = 5$ and $m = 2$ as in second degree polynomial.

$$n = \left(\frac{(5+2-1)!}{(5-1)! 2!} \right) = \frac{6!}{4! 2!} = 15$$

Hence, $n = 15$ signifies that for a (5, 2) simplex lattice design, we have 15 coefficients of the polynomial function, that is 15 experimental runs. The (q-1) factor space will be employed in the design which is a four dimensional space as shown in fig. 1

Fig 1: A (5, 2) Scheffe’s simplex lattice with 15 experimental runs.

The quantities of the five –pseudo components at the fifteen points are follows

- $A_1 (1, 0, 0, 0, 0)$; $A_2 (0, 1, 0, 0, 0)$; $A_3 (0, 0, 1, 0, 0)$; $A_4 (0, 0, 0, 1, 0)$; $A_5 (0, 0, 0, 0, 1)$
- $A_{12} (0.5, 0.5, 0, 0, 0)$; $A_{13} (0.5, 0, 0.5, 0, 0)$; $A_{14} (0.5, 0, 0, 0.5, 0)$; $A_{15} (0.5, 0, 0, 0, 0.5)$
- $A_{23} (0, 0.5, 0.5, 0, 0)$; $A_{24} (0, 0.5, 0, 0.5, 0)$; $A_{25} (0, 0.5, 0, 0, 0.5)$; $A_{34} (0, 0, 0.5, 0.5, 0)$
- $A_{35} (0, 0, 0.5, 0, 0.5)$; $A_{45} (0, 0, 0, 0.5, 0.5)$

According to Ubachukwu and Okafor (2020), the regression equation for a five pseudo component mixture, will be expressed as follows:

$$Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + b_5X_5 + b_{11}X_1^2 + b_{12}X_1X_2 + b_{13}X_1X_3 + b_{14}X_1X_4 + b_{15}X_1X_5 + b_{22}X_2^2 + b_{23}X_2X_3 + b_{24}X_2X_4 + b_{25}X_2X_5 + b_{33}X_3^2 + b_{34}X_3X_4 + b_{35}X_3X_5 + b_{44}X_4^2 + b_{45}X_4X_5 + b_{55}X_5^2 + e \quad (4)$$

- Where y is the response function
- b is the coefficient constants
- x is the independent variables

The term ‘e’ is the random error that represents the combined effects of variables not included in the model.

Multiplying equation (2) by b_0 will be

$$b_0X_1 + b_0X_2 + b_0X_3 + b_0X_4 + b_0X_5 = b_0 \quad (5)$$

Multiplying equation (2) by X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4 and X_5 in succession gives

$$X_1^2 + X_1X_2 + X_1X_3 + X_1X_4 + X_1X_5 = X_1 \quad (6)$$

$$X_1X_2 + X_2^2 + X_2X_3 + X_2X_4 + X_2X_5 = X_2 \quad (7)$$

$$X_1X_3 + X_2X_3 + X_3^2 + X_3X_4 + X_3X_5 = X_3 \quad (8)$$

$$X_1X_4 + X_2X_4 + X_3X_4 + X_4^2 + X_4X_5 = X_4 \quad (9)$$

$$X_1X_5 + X_2X_5 + X_3X_5 + X_4X_5 + X_5^2 = X_5 \quad (10)$$

Rearranging equations (6) - (10) in terms of X_i^2 will become

$$X_1^2 = X_1 - X_1X_2 - X_1X_3 - X_1X_4 - X_1X_5 \quad (11)$$

$$X_2^2 = X_2 - X_1X_2 - X_2X_3 - X_2X_4 - X_2X_5 \quad (12)$$

$$X_3^2 = X_3 - X_1X_3 - X_2X_3 - X_3X_4 - X_3X_5 \quad (13)$$

$$X_4^2 = X_4 - X_1X_4 - X_2X_4 - X_3X_4 - X_4X_5 \quad (14)$$

$$X_5^2 = X_5 - X_1X_5 - X_2X_5 - X_3X_5 - X_4X_5 \quad (15)$$

Substituting equation (5) and equations (11-15) equation (4) will give

$$Y = b_0X_1 + b_0X_2 + b_0X_3 + b_0X_4 + b_0X_5 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + b_5X_5 + b_{11}X_1 - b_{11}X_1X_2 - b_{11}X_1X_3 - b_{11}X_1X_4 - b_{11}X_1X_5 + b_{12}X_1X_2 + b_{13}X_1X_3 + b_{14}X_1X_4 + b_{15}X_1X_5 + b_{22}X_2 - b_{22}X_1X_2 - b_{22}X_2X_3 - b_{22}X_2X_4 - b_{22}X_2X_5 + b_{23}X_2X_3 + b_{24}X_2X_4 + b_{25}X_2X_5 + b_{33}X_3 - b_{33}X_1X_3 - b_{33}X_2X_3 - b_{33}X_3X_4 - b_{33}X_3X_5 + b_{34}X_3X_4 + b_{35}X_3X_5 + b_{44}X_4 - b_{44}X_1X_4 - b_{44}X_2X_4 - b_{44}X_3X_4 - b_{44}X_4X_5 + b_{45}X_4X_5 + b_{55}X_5 - b_{55}X_1X_5 - b_{55}X_2X_5 - b_{55}X_3X_5 - b_{55}X_4X_5 + e \quad (16)$$

Rearranging equation (16) and collecting like terms will give

$$Y = (b_0 + b_1 + b_{11})X_1 + (b_0 + b_2 + b_{22})X_2 + (b_0 + b_3 + b_{33})X_3 + (b_0 + b_4 + b_{44})X_4 + (b_0 + b_5 + b_{55})X_5 + (b_{12} - b_{11} - b_{22})X_1X_2 + (b_{13} - b_{11} - b_{33})X_1X_3 + (b_{14} - b_{11} - b_{44})X_1X_4 + (b_{15} - b_{11} - b_{55})X_1X_5 + (b_{23} - b_{22} - b_{33})X_2X_3 + (b_{24} - b_{22} - b_{44})X_2X_4 + (b_{25} - b_{22} - b_{55})X_2X_5 + (b_{34} - b_{33} - b_{44})X_3X_4 + (b_{35} - b_{33} - b_{55})X_3X_5 + (b_{45} - b_{44} - b_{55})X_4X_5 + e \quad (17)$$

Replacing the constants in equation (17) with 'a' gives

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 &= b_0 + b_1 + b_{11} \\ a_2 &= b_0 + b_2 + b_{22} \\ a_3 &= b_0 + b_3 + b_{33} \\ a_4 &= b_0 + b_4 + b_{44} \\ a_5 &= b_0 + b_5 + b_{55} \\ a_{12} &= b_{12} - b_{11} - b_{22} \\ a_{13} &= b_{13} - b_{11} - b_{33} \\ a_{14} &= b_{14} - b_{11} - b_{44} \\ a_{15} &= b_{15} - b_{11} - b_{55} \\ a_{23} &= b_{23} - b_{22} - b_{33} \\ a_{24} &= b_{24} - b_{22} - b_{44} \\ a_{25} &= b_{25} - b_{22} - b_{55} \\ a_{34} &= b_{34} - b_{33} - b_{44} \\ a_{35} &= b_{35} - b_{33} - b_{55} \\ a_{45} &= b_{45} - b_{44} - b_{55} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Substituting equation (18) into equation (17) gives

$$Y = a_1X_1 + a_2X_2 + a_3X_3 + a_4X_4 + a_5X_5 + a_{12}X_1X_2 + a_{13}X_1X_3 + a_{14}X_1X_4 + a_{15}X_1X_5 + a_{23}X_2X_3 + a_{24}X_2X_4 + a_{25}X_2X_5 + a_{34}X_3X_4 + a_{35}X_3X_5 + a_{45}X_4X_5 + e \quad (19)$$

Equation (19) can be rewritten as

$$Y = \hat{Y} + e \quad (20)$$

Where e = standard error

$$\hat{Y} = a_1X_1 + a_2X_2 + a_3X_3 + a_4X_4 + a_5X_5 + a_{12}X_1X_2 + a_{13}X_1X_3 + a_{14}X_1X_4 + a_{15}X_1X_5$$

$$+ a_{23}X_2X_3 + a_{24}X_2X_4 + a_{25}X_2X_5 + a_{34}X_3X_4 + a_{35}X_3X_5 + a_{45}X_4X_5 \quad (21)$$

Equation (21) is the Scheffe's (5, 2) lattice polynomial equation. The response functions (compressive strengths) are obtained by carrying out a total of fifteen tests in the laboratory.

The determination of the values of the coefficients in equation (21) will complete the model equation by substituting the pseudo mix values. Where:

$$a_1 = y_1 \quad (22)$$

$$a_2 = y_2 \quad (23)$$

$$a_3 = y_3 \quad (24)$$

$$a_4 = y_4 \quad (25)$$

$$a_5 = y_5 \quad (26)$$

$$a_{12} = 4y_2 - 2y_1 - 2y_2 \quad (27)$$

$$a_{13} = 4y_{13} = 2y_1 - 2y_3 \quad (28)$$

$$a_{14} = 4y_{14} - 2y_1 - 2y_4 \quad (29)$$

$$a_{15} = 4y_{15} - 2y_1 - 2y_5 \quad (30)$$

$$a_{23} = 4y_{23} - 2y_2 - 2y_3 \quad (31)$$

$$a_{24} = 4y_{24} - 2y_2 - 2y_4 \quad (32)$$

$$a_{25} = 4y_{25} - 2y_2 - 2y_5 \quad (33)$$

$$a_{34} = 4y_{34} - 2y_3 - 2y_4 \quad (34)$$

$$a_{35} = 4y_{35} - 2y_3 - 2y_5 \quad (35)$$

$$a_{45} = 4y_{45} - 2y_4 - 2y_5 \quad (36)$$

Concrete Mix Ratios for the Model Formulation

According to Mbadike and Osadebe (2014), the relationship between the actual and the pseudo mix ratios are given by

$$\{Z\} = [A] \{X\} \quad (37)$$

$$\{X\} = [A^{-1}] \{Z\} \quad (38)$$

Where Z, A and X are the real mix ratios, coefficient of relation matrix and pseudo mix ratios respectively. The value of matrix A will be obtained by substituting the values of the first five real mix ratios which are: Z₁ (0.50: 0.95: 2.00: 4.00: 0.05); Z₂ (0.55: 0.90: 1.90: 3.90: 0.10); Z₃ (0.60: 0.85: 2.10: 4.10: 0.15); Z₄ (0.65: 0.80: 2.30: 3.80: 0.20); Z₅ (0.70: 0.75: 1.70: 3.70: 0.25) and the corresponding pseudo mix ratios at the vertices of the simplex lattice X₁ (1 : 0 : 0 : 0 : 0); X₂ (0 : 1 : 0 : 0 : 0); X₃ (0 : 0 : 1 : 0 : 0); X₄ (0 : 0 : 0 : 1 : 0); X₅ (0 : 0 : 0 : 0 : 1) into equation 37.

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 0.50 & 0.55 & 0.60 & 0.65 & 0.70 \\ 0.95 & 0.90 & 0.85 & 0.80 & 0.75 \\ 2.00 & 1.90 & 2.10 & 2.30 & 1.70 \\ 4.00 & 3.90 & 4.10 & 3.80 & 3.70 \\ 0.05 & 0.10 & 0.15 & 0.20 & 0.25 \end{pmatrix} \quad (39)$$

Also, substituting the other pseudo mix ratios at the midpoint of the simplex lattice into Eq. (37), the remaining ten (10) real mix ratios were obtained. Hence, the real mix ratios and pseudo mix ratios at the vertices and midpoints of the simplex lattice are as given in table 1. In order to validate

the model for the compressive strength of RHA concrete at 28 days curing age, 15 additional control mixes were made as shown in table 2. A total of ninety (90) 150mm x 150mm x 150mm concrete cubes were produced and used for the research. 45 cubes each were used for both the response and control points' experiments respectively.

Table 3.1: Design matrix for Scheffe's (5, 2) lattice

S/N	Actual					Response	Pseudo				
	Z ₁	Z ₂	Z ₃	Z ₄	Z ₅		X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄	X ₅
1	0.5	0.95	2.0	4.0	0.05	Y ₁	1	0	0	0	0
2	0.55	0.90	1.90	3.90	0.10	Y ₂	0	1	0	0	0
3	0.60	0.85	2.10	4.10	0.15	Y ₃	0	0	1	0	0
4	0.65	0.80	2.30	3.80	0.20	Y ₄	0	0	0	1	0
5	0.70	0.75	1.70	3.70	0.25	Y ₅	0	0	0	0	1
12	0.525	0.925	1.95	3.95	0.075	Y ₁₂	0.5	0.5	0	0	0
13	0.55	0.90	2.05	4.05	0.10	Y ₁₃	0.5	0	0.5	0	0
14	0.575	0.875	2.15	3.90	0.125	Y ₁₄	0.5	0	0	0.5	0
15	0.60	0.85	1.85	3.85	0.15	Y ₁₅	0.5	0	0	0	0.5
23	0.575	0.875	2.00	4.00	0.125	Y ₂₃	0	0.5	0.5	0	0
24	0.60	0.85	2.10	3.85	0.15	Y ₂₄	0	0.5	0	0.5	0
25	0.625	0.825	1.80	3.80	0.175	Y ₂₅	0	0.5	0	0	0.5
34	0.625	0.825	2.20	3.95	0.175	Y ₃₄	0	0	0.5	0.5	0
35	0.65	0.80	1.90	3.90	0.20	Y ₃₅	0	0	0.5	0	0.5
45	0.675	0.775	2.0	3.75	0.225	Y ₄₅	0	0	0	0.5	0.5

Table 3.2: Mixture Proportions of control points showing actual and pseudo component

S/N	Actual					Response	Pseudo				
	Z ₁	Z ₂	Z ₃	Z ₄	Z ₅		X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄	X ₅
1	0.575	0.875	2.075	3.950	0.125	C ₁	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0
2	0.5875	0.8625	1.925	3.925	0.1375	C ₂	0.25	0.25	0.25	0	0.25
3	0.6	0.85	1.975	3.85	0.15	C ₃	0.25	0.25	0	0.25	0.25
4	0.6125	0.8375	2.025	3.90	0.1625	C ₄	0.25	0	0.25	0.25	0.25
5	0.625	0.825	2.00	3.875	0.175	C ₅	0	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
12	0.60	0.85	2.00	3.90	0.15	C ₁₂	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
13	0.56	0.89	2.03	3.98	0.11	C ₁₃	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.1	0
14	0.565	0.885	1.97	3.97	0.115	C ₁₄	0.3	0.3	0.3	0	0.1
15	0.58	0.87	2.03	3.88	0.13	C ₁₅	0.3	0.3	0	0.3	0.1
23	0.595	0.855	2.09	3.94	0.145	C ₂₃	0.3	0	0.3	0.3	0.1
24	0.61	0.84	2.06	3.91	0.16	C ₂₄	0	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.1
25	0.635	0.815	2.03	3.88	0.185	C ₂₅	0.1	0	0.3	0.3	0.3
34	0.62	0.83	1.97	3.82	0.17	C ₃₄	0.1	0.3	0	0.3	0.3
35	0.605	0.845	1.91	3.91	0.155	C ₃₅	0.1	0.3	0.3	0	0.3
45	0.59	0.86	2.09	3.94	0.14	C ₄₅	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.3	0

Results and Discussion

Compressive Strength Results

Table 3 and table 4 show the 28-days compressive strength result of RHA concrete mixture materials obtain from the laboratory tests for both the response and control points.

Table 3: 28-days Compressive Strength Results for the Response (Y_i)

Response	Replicate	Average mass (kg)	Volume (m ³)	Average Bulk Density (kg/m ³)	Crusting load (KN)	Compressive strength N/mm ²	Average compressive strength
Y ₁	A	8.15	0.003375	2414.81	579	25.73	28.27
	B				688	30.58	
	C				641	28.49	
Y ₂	A	7.94	0.003375	2352.59	473	21.02	23.13
	B				512	22.76	
	C				576	25.60	
Y ₃	A	7.86	0.003375	2328.89	524	23.29	21.35
	B				449	19.96	
	C				468	20.80	
Y ₄	A	7.78	0.003375	2305.19	453	20.13	20.56
	B				483	21.47	
	C				452	20.09	
Y ₅	A	7.71	0.003375	2284.44	434	19.29	19.33
	B				466	20.71	
	C				408	18.13	
Y ₁₂	A	8.07	0.003375	2391.11	614	27.29	27.61
	B				647	28.76	
	C				603	26.80	
Y ₁₃	A	8.01	0.003375	2373.33	559	24.84	24.35
	B				531	23.60	
	C				554	24.62	
Y ₁₄	A	7.98	0.003375	2364.44	549	24.40	23.69
	B				517	22.98	
	C				533	23.69	
Y ₁₅	A	7.89	0.003375	2337.78	510	22.67	21.51
	B				469	20.84	
	C				473	21.02	
Y ₂₃	A	7.91	0.003375	2343.70	505	22.44	22.25
	B				453	20.13	
	C				544	24.18	
Y ₂₄	A	7.92	0.003375	2346.67	499	22.18	21.32
	B				465	20.67	
	C				475	21.11	
Y ₂₅	A	7.85	0.003375	2325.93	452	20.09	20.65
	B				486	21.60	
	C				456	20.27	
Y ₃₄	A	7.80	0.003375	2311.11	485	21.56	20.51
	B				459	20.40	
	C				440	19.56	
Y ₃₅	A	7.75	0.003375	2296.30	461	20.49	19.94
	B				419	18.62	
	C				466	20.71	
Y ₄₅	A	7.73	0.003375	2290.37	403	17.91	19.46
	B				447	19.86	
	C				464	20.62	

Table 4: 28-days Compressive Strength Results for the Control Points

Response	Replicate	Average mass (kg)	Volume (m ³)	Average Bulk Density (kg/m ³)	Crusting load (KN)	Compressive strength N/mm ²	Average compressive strength
C ₁	A	7.96	0.003375	2358.52	529	23.51	23.88
	B				537	23.87	
	C				546	24.27	
C ₂	A	7.91	0.003375	2343.70	488	21.69	22.80
	B				524	23.29	
	C				527	23.42	
C ₃	A	7.87	0.003375	2331.85	496	22.04	21.45
	B				487	21.64	
	C				465	20.67	
C ₄	A	7.83	0.003375	2320.00	482	21.42	20.93
	B				450	20.00	
	C				481	21.38	
C ₅	A	7.81	0.003375	2314.07	467	20.76	20.56
	B				442	19.64	
	C				479	21.29	
C ₁₂	A	8.01	0.003375	2373.33	536	23.82	24.65
	B				567	25.20	
	C				561	24.93	
C ₁₃	A	8.03	0.003375	2379.26	578	25.69	25.82
	B				559	24.84	
	C				606	26.93	
C ₁₄	A	8.09	0.003375	2397.04	611	27.16	26.08
	B				582	25.87	
	C				567	25.20	
C ₁₅	A	7.93	0.003375	2349.63	523	23.24	23.73
	B				552	24.53	
	C				527	23.42	
C ₂₃	A	7.91	0.003375	2343.70	530	23.56	23.13
	B				494	21.96	
	C				537	23.87	
C ₂₄	A	7.89	0.003375	2337.78	478	21.24	21.06
	B				475	21.11	
	C				469	20.84	
C ₂₅	A	7.71	0.003375	2284.44	451	20.04	19.73
	B				441	19.50	
	C				440	19.56	
C ₃₄	A	7.74	0.003375	2293.33	439	19.51	19.96
	B				447	19.87	
	C				461	20.49	
C ₃₅	A	7.83	0.003375	2320.00	474	21.07	20.87
	B				464	20.62	
	C				471	20.93	
C ₄₅	A	7.91	0.003375	2343.70	493	21.91	22.34
	B				508	22.58	
	C				507	22.53	

Regression Model for Compressive Strength of RHA Concrete

The coefficients of the Scheffe’s regression equation for the compressive strength of RHA concrete was obtained from equations (22) – (36) and the results were presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Coefficient of Scheffe’s Second Degree Polynomial for the Regression Model.

a ₁	a ₂	a ₃	a ₄	a ₅	a ₁₂	a ₁₃	a ₁₄	a ₁₅	a ₂₃	a ₂₄	a ₂₅	a ₃₄	a ₃₅	a ₄₅
28.27	23.13	21.35	20.56	19.38	7.64	-1.84	-2.9	-9.26	0.04	-2.1	-2.42	-1.78	-1.70	-2.04

Substituting the values of these coefficients into equation (21) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{Y} = & 28.27X_1 + 23.13X_2 + 21.35X_3 + 20.56X_4 + 19.38X_5 + 7.64X_1X_2 - 1.84X_1X_3 \\ & - 2.90X_1X_4 - 9.26X_1X_5 + 0.04X_2X_3 - 2.10X_2X_4 - 2.42X_2X_5 - 1.78X_3X_4 - 1.70X_3X_5 \\ & - 2.04X_4X_5 \end{aligned} \tag{40}$$

Equation (40) is the regression model for the compressive strength of RHA concrete. The Scheffe’s model test results for compressive strength are obtained when the pseudo mix ratios presented in tables 1 and 2 are substituted in equation (40). Table 6 shows the experimental test results and Scheffe’s model test result.

Table 6: Experimental Test Result and Scheffe’s Model Test Result

Symbol	Experimental test result	Scheffe’s model test result
Y ₁	28.27	28.27
Y ₂	23.13	23.13
Y ₃	21.35	21.35
Y ₄	20.56	20.56
Y ₅	19.38	19.38
Y ₁₂	27.61	27.61
Y ₁₃	24.35	24.35
Y ₁₄	23.69	23.69
Y ₁₅	21.51	21.51
Y ₂₃	22.25	22.25
Y ₂₄	21.32	21.32
Y ₂₅	20.65	20.65
Y ₃₄	20.51	20.51
Y ₃₅	19.94	19.94
Y ₄₅	19.46	19.46
C ₁	23.88	23.27
C ₂	22.80	22.56
C ₃	21.45	22.15
C ₄	20.93	21.17
C ₅	20.56	20.49
C ₁₂	24.65	21.89
C ₁₃	25.82	24.20
C ₁₄	26.08	23.89
C ₁₅	23.73	23.36
C ₂₃	23.13	22.02
C ₂₄	21.06	20.92
C ₂₅	19.73	20.29
C ₃₄	19.96	21.03
C ₃₅	20.87	21.52
C ₄₅	22.34	22.08

Test for Model Adequacy

The test for adequacy of the model was done using Fisher's test at 95% confidence level on the compressive strength at the control points subject to these two hypotheses:

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between the laboratory tests and the predicted model strength results.

Alternative Hypothesis: There is a significant difference between the laboratory test and predicted model strength results.

The Fisher's test was used to validate the adequacy of the model using the two tailed test and rejecting the null hypothesis if $F_{cal} > F_{critical}$ based on results presented in Table 7

Table 7: Fisher's Test Result for the controlled compressive strength of RHA concrete.

Symbol	Y_e	Y_m	$Y_e - Y_{ee}$	$Y_m - Y_{mm}$	$(Y_e - Y_{ee})$	$(Y_m - Y_{mm})^2$
C ₁	23.88	23.27	1.71	1.21	2.92	1.46
C ₂	22.80	22.56	0.63	0.50	0.40	0.25
C ₃	21.45	22.15	-0.72	0.09	0.52	0.01
C ₄	20.93	21.17	-1.24	-0.89	1.54	0.79
C ₅	20.56	20.49	-1.61	-1.57	2.59	2.46
C ₁₂	22.65	21.89	0.48	-0.17	0.23	0.03
C ₁₃	24.82	24.20	2.65	2.14	7.02	4.58
C ₁₄	25.08	23.39	2.91	1.83	8.47	3.35
C ₁₅	23.73	23.36	1.56	1.30	2.43	1.69
C ₂₃	22.68	22.02	0.51	-0.04	0.26	0.00
C ₂₄	21.06	20.92	-1.11	-1.14	1.23	1.30
C ₂₅	19.73	20.29	-2.44	-1.77	5.95	3.13
C ₃₄	19.96	21.03	-2.21	-1.03	4.88	1.06
C ₃₅	20.87	21.52	-1.30	-0.54	1.69	0.29
C ₄₅	22.34	22.08	0.17	0.02	0.03	0.00
Total	332.54	330.84			40.16	20.40
Mean	22.17	22.06				

Where Y_e = experimental control result

Y_m = Model control result

$$Y_{ee} = \frac{\sum y_e}{N} = \frac{332.54}{15} = 22.17$$

$$Y_{mm} = \frac{\sum y_m}{N} = \frac{330.84}{15} = 22.06$$

$$S_e^2 = \frac{\sum (y_e - y_{ee})^2}{N - 1} = \frac{40.16}{15 - 1} = 2.87$$

$$S_m^2 = \frac{\sum (y_m - y_{mm})^2}{N - 1} = \frac{20.40}{15 - 1} = 1.46$$

S_1^2 is the greater of S_e^2 and S_m^2

S_2^2 is the least of S_e^2 and S_m^2

Therefore, $S_1^2 = 2.87$ and $S_2^2 = 1.46$

$$\text{Hence, } F_{\text{cal}} = \frac{S_1^2}{S_2^2} = \frac{2.87}{1.46} = 1.97$$

But $F_{\text{critical}} = F_{\alpha}(v_1, v_2)$

Where α is the significant level and v is the degree of freedom.

Therefore, $F_{(0.05)(14,14)} = 2.48$ (obtained from the table by interpolation)

$$(F_{\text{critical}})^{-1} = (2.48)^{-1} = 0.40$$

Therefore $0.40 < 1.97 < 2.48$

Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted and the model is adequate for use.

Discussion of Results

The values of the compressive strength of RHA concrete were obtained using the Scheffe's model as given in equation (40). The model gave the highest compressive strength of 28.27N/mm² corresponding to a mix ratio of 0.50:0.95:2.00:4.00:0.05 for w/c ratio, cement, sand, granite and RHA respectively and the minimum compressive strength of the model was found to be 19.38N/mm² corresponding to a mix ratio of 0.70:0.75:1.70:3.70:0.25. The model formulated for the RHA concrete was validated using the Fisher's test to check the model adequacy. The results revealed that there was no significant difference between the laboratory test results and Scheffe's model predicted results. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted and the model validated was adequate. The results also revealed that the compressive strength reduces as the RHA used as partial replacement of cement increased due to the high water demand needed for the concrete mix to be workable and the fineness of the RHA content. The findings were similar to the results of Khan & Siddique (2012) and Single & Siddique (2013) indicating that the proportion of RHA in concrete mix design affects the compressive strength of concrete. The proper utilization of RHA in concrete mix design also offers both economic and environmental benefits as it helps to reduce the cost of concrete production through the partial replacement of cement with about 17.5 percent RHA content to produce grade C20 concrete as shown in table 6, minimizes the emission of carbon dioxide (CO₂) during construction, reduces waste and enhances effective disposal of the RHA.

Conclusion

The following conclusions were made.

- (1) The Scheffe's model formulated was adequate and reliable at 95% confidence level for predicting the compressive strength of RHA concrete
- (2) The model gave the highest compressive strength of 28.27 N/mm² corresponding to a mix ratio of 0.50:0.95:2.00:4.00:0.05 for w/c ratio, cement, sand, granite and RHA respectively and the minimum compressive strength of 19.38N/mm² corresponding to mix ratio of 0.70:0.75:1.70:3.70:0.25 for w/c ratio, cement, sand, granite and RHA respectively.
- (3) RHA can be used as fifth component of concrete based on the regression model formulated and will help to both reduce the cost of cement during concrete production and carbon emissions in construction.

Recommendation

The regression model formulated can be used to produce grade C20 concrete provided that the RHA content used as partial replacement of cement does not exceed 17.5 percent.

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